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Distinct non-photochemical quenching characteristics under constant and fluctuating light conditions: comparison between local and imported tobacco varieties

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Abstract:	<p>To explore the variation in adaptability to fluctuating light environments and optimize their photosynthesis and growth, the non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) characteristics of a local tobacco variety Xiaofeng 8 and a foreign introduced variety K326, under both constant and fluctuating light conditions were examined. Under high light intensities, Xiaofeng 8 exhibited a higher NPQ value compared to K326, indicating an enhanced capacity for dissipating excess light energy as thermal energy and mitigating the potential risk of photodamage. The induction changes of NPQ and photosystem II efficiency (ΦPSII) from dark to low and high light conditions were analyzed, revealing distinct adaptability to high light environments and associated photoprotection mechanisms in Xiaofeng 8. While Xiaofeng 8 induced the regulatory non-photochemical quenching in high light, K326 realized the protection by the constitutive non-photochemical quenching, which preserved also to low light conditions and seem to be the reason for a lower growth of K326 than of Xiaofeng 8 in natural light condition, i.e., under fluctuating light. Additionally, the role of xanthophyll cycle pigments in regulating NPQ and energy dissipation under high light intensities was examined using mutants defective in violaxanthin de-epoxidase (VDE) and zeaxanthin epoxidase (ZEP). The results showed that defects in these enzymes affected the NPQ response and reduced the growth rate of the mutants under fluctuating light conditions, suggesting a crucial role of the xanthophyll cycle in plant growth and adaptation to variable light environments. Collectively, these findings emphasize the importance of exploring genetic resources improving plant NPQ under fluctuating light conditions from both domestic and imported varieties, thereby providing promising targets for selecting and breeding new crop varieties with improved yield, quality, and resistance, ultimately enhancing breeding efficiency and crop adaptability.</p>

1 **Distinct non-photochemical quenching characteristics under constant and fluctuating light**
2 **conditions: comparison between local and imported tobacco varieties**

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1 **Abstract:** To explore the variation in adaptability to fluctuating light environments and optimize their
2 photosynthesis and growth, the non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) characteristics of a local tobacco
3 variety Xiaofeng 8 and a foreign introduced variety K326, under both constant and fluctuating light
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5 compared to K326, indicating an enhanced capacity for dissipating excess light energy as thermal energy
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7 efficiency (Φ PSII) from dark to low and high light conditions were analyzed, revealing distinct
8 adaptability to high light environments and associated photoprotection mechanisms in Xiaofeng 8. While
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10 protection by the constitutive non-photochemical quenching, which preserved also to low light
11 conditions and seem to be the reason for a lower growth of K326 than of Xiaofeng 8 in natural light
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13 NPQ and energy dissipation under high light intensities was examined using mutants defective in
14 violaxanthin de-epoxidase (VDE) and zeaxanthin epoxidase (ZEP). The results showed that defects in
15 these enzymes affected the NPQ response and reduced the growth rate of the mutants under fluctuating
16 light conditions, suggesting a crucial role of the xanthophyll cycle in plant growth and adaptation to
17 variable light environments. Collectively, these findings emphasize the importance of exploring genetic
18 resources improving plant NPQ under fluctuating light conditions from both domestic and imported
19 varieties, thereby providing promising targets for selecting and breeding new crop varieties with
20 improved yield, quality, and resistance, ultimately enhancing breeding efficiency and crop adaptability.
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43 **Key words:** non-photochemical quenching; local and imported varieties; fluctuating light; xanthophyll
44 cycle; tobacco
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Introduction

In natural environments, plants often face fluctuations in light intensity due to various factors such as cloud cover, leaf movement in the wind, plant shading and changes in solar angle (Long et al., 2006; Taylor and Long, 2017). This fluctuation in light intensity can lead to rapid changes in the intensity of light received by plant leaves, have a significant impact on the photosynthesis of plants. On the one hand, fluctuations in light intensity can affect the rate and efficiency of photosynthesis in plants, thereby affecting their growth, development, and yield (Slattery et al., 2018). On the other hand, with the rapid increase in light intensity, when plants absorb more light energy than they need for photosynthesis, the excess light energy may cause damage to plant cells (Shi et al., 2022; Shafiq et al., 2021).

To cope with such challenges, plants have evolved various photoprotective mechanisms, among which the energy dependent non-photochemical quenching (qE) plays a crucial role (Bielczynski et al., 2017; Shi et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2022; Niu et al., 2023). The qE is a rapidly inducible process that enables plants to dissipate excess absorbed light energy as heat, thereby protecting their photosynthetic apparatus from photodamage (Nicol et al., 2019). The qE requires low pH of thylakoid lumen to protonate PSII subunit S (PsbS) (Brooks et al., 2014; Li et al., 2000) and to activate violaxanthin-deepoxidase (VDE), which converts violaxanthin (V) via antheraxanthin (A) to zeaxanthin (Z) (Demmig-Adams 1990; Yamamoto et al., 1962).

Due to different genetic characteristics and photosynthetic mechanisms, there are differences in the qE mechanisms of plant varieties from different regions and genotypes (Tanaka et al., 2019). For example, overexpression of three transgenes (*AtVDE*, *AtPsbS*, and *AtZEP*) in soybean and tobacco, which are required to enhance setting and decay of qE under high light or rapidly fluctuating conditions as widely described previously, accelerated the relaxation of NPQ during sun-to-shade transitions, resulting in increased photosynthetic efficiency and crop productivity under fluctuating light (Kromdijk et al., 2016; De Souza et al., 2022). At the same time, it was found that some rice and corn varieties have higher NPQ ability, which can better dissipate excess light energy, protect the photosynthetic system from light damage, maintain high photosynthetic rate and yield, while other varieties cannot effectively cope with high light induced photodamage, resulting in a decrease in photosynthetic rate and yield (Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017; Tsai et al., 2019). There are differences in the NPQ ability of plant varieties with different origins to high light, which are mainly due to the different genetic backgrounds, and evolutionary histories of their respective growth environments. Understanding these differences helps us

1 to better understand the photosynthesis mechanism and photoprotection strategies of plants, providing
2 scientific basis and technical support for agricultural production. While NPQ has been extensively
3 studied under stable light conditions, it is important to note that plants often face fluctuations in light
4 intensity in nature, as described earlier. Therefore, understanding the NPQ response of plants under
5 fluctuating light conditions is of great significance. By studying the response of NPQ to fluctuating light,
6 we can better understand how plants adapt to these environmental changes, and how to improve plant
7 stress resistance, photosynthetic efficiency, and yield through genetic engineering and other means,
8 providing new solutions for ensuring global food security.
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11 Tobacco is well-known as a smoking material but it has always been considered as a medicinal plant
12 and used as a traditional medicine for common illnesses (Charlton 2004, Berlowitz et al. 2020). In present
13 knowledge, nicotine contained in tobacco is an agonist to acetylcholine, the later being natural chemical
14 involved in ligand-gated nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, i.e. ligand-gated ion channels. These ion
15 channels are indispensable for proper transmission of electric signals in synapses between neurons and
16 neuron and muscle cells (Hogg et al. 2003) Tobacco plants can be also used as a natural living laboratory
17 to produce human therapeutic reagents (Sanchez-Ramos 2020). These facts indicate that planting tobacco
18 might be useful but it is important to know, which variety of tobacco best survives in the environment.
19 Xiaofeng 8 is a common tobacco variety in Guizhou, China. It is characterized by a more robust growth
20 rate in the field and a higher productivity of biomass. On the other hand, K326 tobacco variety was
21 exported to China. This variety is resistant to the common root-knot nematodes and it is known for high
22 quality and curability (see <https://crosscreekseed.com/usa-varieties/usa-flue-cured-tobacco-seed/k-326/>).
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41 In this work, we studied if the seemingly superior K326 variant is better in grown in the field, i.e.,
42 under fluctuating light conditions. Namely, we investigate the NPQ characteristics of two tobacco
43 cultivars, Xiaofeng 8 and K326, under both constant and fluctuating light conditions. By comparing their
44 NPQ responses, we aimed to gain insights into how plants adapt to fluctuating light environments and
45 optimize their photosynthesis and growth. Furthermore, we also examined the role of xanthophyll cycle
46 pigments in regulating NPQ and energy dissipation under high light intensities. Our findings provided
47 valuable insights into the photoprotective strategies of plants and have implications for crop breeding
48 and genetic engineering to improve photosynthetic efficiency and yield under fluctuating light conditions.
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59 **Materials and methods**

Plant materials and growth conditions

For the field experiment, the tobacco cultivars Xiaofeng 8, a local landrace, and K326 that introduced from USA, were selected as study materials on the basis of plant size and growth rate according to previous observations. The trial was conducted in Qingzhen (lat. 26°31'27"N, long. 107°21'16"E) in 2022, at an altitude of 1280 m, in Guizhou, China. Ten-day average temperature and 10-day sunshine hour records from March to October are presented in Fig. 1. Note: what is 10-day average temperature and ten-day sunshine hour? Specify it differently so that it is clear what you mean. The soil properties (0–20 cm) at the study site are presented in Lin et al. (2020). Seeds were sown in an open greenhouse on 25 Feb. 2022 on transplanting disks as described previously in detail (Lin et al., 2017). A series of agricultural operations, including turning up the soil, ridging, plastic mulching, and planting hole preparation, were carried out as described previously in detail (Lin et al., 2015, 2017). Seedlings were transplanted into the test plots (15×7 m) with three replicates for each genotype on 26 Apr. 2023. For detailed observations and measurements, fifteen plants were randomly selected from both cultivars.

The *vde* (LOC104218706) and *zep* (LOC104218557) knockout mutant were generated from Biorun Biosciences (Wuhan, China) by CRISPR–Cas9, using a single-guide RNA. To investigate the effects of xanthophyll cycle on seedlings pigments, NPQ characteristic and growth under fluctuating light conditions, confirmed *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant seeds were sown as described previously in detail (Lin et al., 2017). Seedlings that were 45-day old were transplanted to plastic pots (diameter 7 cm; height 7 cm) filled with organic soil and maintained in a growth chamber with a 16/8 light/dark cycle. A constant light intensity of 1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ was set for pigments and NPQ characteristic investigation while the light intensity for growth phenotype experiment was set to fluctuate every 3 min, randomly among 70, 400, 700, 900 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ with an overall fractional contribution of 0.1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, respectively, which ensured the average light intensity was close to 600 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence measurements

Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence (ChlF) was measured using a portable gas exchange system LI-6400XT (Licor Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). The kinetics were first recorded on attached leaves of 30 min dark-adapted plants using actinic red light 70 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (low light) or 1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (high light) for 6 min. For experiments in fluctuating light, attached leaves of 30-min dark-adapted plants were illuminated for four cycles of 3 min low light (70 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and 3 min high light (1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), NPQ induction and relaxation were monitored at 20 s intervals.

1 The following parameters were determined from measured ChlF values (see Lazár 2015 for a review):
2 effective quantum yield of PSII photochemistry in light-adapted state (Φ_{PSII}) calculated as $(F_m' - F)/F_m'$,
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4 relative PSII electron transport rate (ETR) as $\Phi_{PSII} \times PAR \times 0.84 \times 0.5$, and non-photochemical quenching
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6 parameter (NPQ) as $(F_m - F_m')/F_m'$, where F_m is maximum ChlF in dark-adapted state, F_m' is maximum
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8 ChlF in light-adapted state, and F is ChlF in the actinic light.
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10 **Assays of Plant growth**

11 Leaf area was measured using the fresh leaf by Area meter (AM 300, ADC Bio-scientific Ltd., UK) and
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13 replicated for three times with 5 seedlings per replicate. Number of leaves was surveyed at different time
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15 for leaf number determination. Plant height was measured by the distance from the first leaf base from
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17 bottom to the growing points of shoots (the apical meristems). The dry weight (DW) of the leaves was
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19 determined using the mass method after drying the plants at 105°C for 48 h.
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22 **Leaf pigment analysis**

23 Pigments were analysed by reverse-phase-performance liquid chromatography. For pigments extraction,
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25 leaf discs were frozen in liquid nitrogen and suspended in KOH methanol solution (20%), keep at 55 °C
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27 for 30 minutes. Extraction solution (acetone: ethyl acetate=1:2, v/v) was added after cooling and
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29 ultrasonic extraction for 40 minutes. After centrifuge for 15 (4 °C, 8000 g), The supernatant was
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31 evaporated to dryness. After diluted with acetone, extracted pigments were filtered through a membrane
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33 filter (pore size 0.2 μ m), and used for high-performance liquid chromatography analysis. The contents
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35 of Leaf pigments were measured simultaneously using a Welch Ultimate C30 (5 μ m, 4.6 \times 250 mm)
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37 (Welch, Shanghai, China) with detection wavelength and column flow rate were 450nm and 1.0ml/min,
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39 respectively. The xanthophyll cycle de-epoxidation state (DEPS) has been shown to have a better linear
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41 relationship with plant heat dissipation capacity, and it was calculated as $DEPS = (Z + 0.5A) / (V + Z + A)$
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43 (Johnson et al., 1993).
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47 **The data analysis**

48 Data analysis software SPSS 17.0 was used for one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and the
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50 significant differences between genotype were indicated with different lowercase letters ($P \leq 0.05$).
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52 Statistical data were expressed as average value \pm standard error (SE).
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56 **Results**

57 **Seedlings of Xiaofeng 8 grew faster in the field experiment**

1 After being transplanted for 20 d, significant phenotypic differences were observed between seedlings
2 of Xiaofeng 8 and K326 (Fig. 2A). In terms of plant height, K326 exhibits a significantly lower growth
3 than Xiaofeng 8, which indicates a more vigorous vertical growth pattern in Xiaofeng 8 compared to
4 K326 (Fig. 2D). Other growth parameters such as leaf number, maximum leaf area, and fresh weight of
5 Xiaofeng 8 were significantly higher than those ones of K326 (Fig. 2B, C, E and F). Overall, Xiaofeng
6 8 shows a more robust growth pattern compared to K326.

12 **A stronger ability to dissipate excess light energy in Xiaofeng 8 under high light intensity**

13 To investigate the photosynthetic acclimation of the two tobacco varieties to different light conditions,
14 induction of NPQ parameter and effective quantum yield of PSII photochemistry, Φ_{PSII} , during the dark
15 to low and high constant light conditions were analyzed. During the first 40 seconds on a shift from dark
16 to low light conditions ($70 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), value of NPQ parameter increased and then gradually
17 decreased in K326 seedlings, while the NPQ parameter gradually decreased in Xiaofeng 8 seedlings (Fig.
18 3A). On the other hand, a rapid increase in NPQ were observed in both K326 and Xiaofeng 8 seedlings
19 on shift from dark to high light condition ($1000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), while the steady state value of
20 NPQ in Xiaofeng 8 was higher than those of K326 (Fig. 3B). Quantum yield of PSII photochemistry in
21 light-adapted state (Φ_{PSII}) of both K326 and Xiaofeng 8 initially decreased on shift from dark to both
22 low and high light, followed by an increase with increasing time (Fig. 3C and D). While the initial
23 decrease was more pronounced upon transition to high light than to low light, the following increase was
24 higher upon transition to low light than to high light. Nevertheless, no obvious differences were detected
25 in changes of Φ_{PSII} between the two varieties under same light intensity (Fig. 3C and D).

26 More detailed exploration of dependence of the steady-state values of the NPQ parameters, Φ_{PSII} ,
27 and of the relative PSII electron transport rate (ETR) on intensities of illumination by constant
28 photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) is presented in Fig. 4. There is no significant difference in ETR
29 and Φ_{PSII} between K326 and Xiaofeng 8 varieties during exposure to an increasing amount of constant
30 PAR (Fig. 4A and 4B) and the same is true for the NPQ parameter at PAR levels $< 600 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}$
31 s^{-1} (Fig. 4C). However, a higher steady state NPQ values were detected at constant PAR $> 400 \mu\text{mol}$
32 $\text{photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in Xiaofeng 8 than those of K326 (Fig. 4C).

33 **Characteristics of NPQ and Φ_{PSII} in fluctuating light in K326 and Xiaofeng 8**

1 To investigate the response of NPQ parameter to continuously fluctuating light, seedling leaves of both
2 two tobacco varieties were exposed to alternating cycles of 180 s at high light and 180 s low light. As for
3 the dark-to-low light transition, Xiaofeng 8 displayed insignificantly lower NPQ parameter value
4 compared with those of K326. After transitions from low to high light of every alternating cycle, value
5 of NPQ parameter of Xiaofeng 8 increased rapidly and reached a higher level than those of K326, and
6 this pattern was also detected during the rest high light period throughout the entire light cycle. After
7 transitions from high to low light, the value of NPQ parameter decreased rapidly and no obvious change
8 were detected between K326 and Xiaofeng 8 (Fig. 5A). Interestingly, no obvious change were detected
9 in Φ PSII between the two plants throughout the entire low-high light cycle (Fig. 5B). During low light
10 periods, the value of Φ PSII is relatively high. However, when the light intensity increases to high light,
11 the Φ PSII value rapidly decreases.

22 **Responses of xanthophyll cycle pigments in K326 and Xiaofeng 8 to high light**

23 In order to underlie the mechanisms regulating their ability to dissipate excess light energy under high
24 light, response pattern of xanthophyll cycle pigments in K326 and Xiaofeng 8 seedlings were analyzed
25 after exposure to high light ($1000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The results showed that, no significant difference
26 were detected in the three pigments, and the DEPS state between the two varieties in dark. After exposure
27 to high light, the content of V in Xiaofeng 8 decreased rapidly within the first 10 min and reduced to half
28 at most after 10 min. On the other hand, the contents of A, and Z were increased after transition from
29 dark to high light (Fig. 6). The pattern of changes of xanthophyll cycle pigments in K326 is similar to
30 that of Xiaofeng 8, except that the content of V is lower in Xiaofeng 8 than in K326 in high light and
31 content of A, Z, and DEPS is higher in Xiaofeng 8 than in K326 in high light (Fig 6).

43 **Altered xanthophyll cycle pigments affected seedlings NPQ under high light intensity**

44 To further investigate the role of xanthophyll cycle pigments in regulating plants ability to dissipate
45 excess energy under rapidly fluctuating light conditions, mutants with malfunctional VDE or zeaxanthin-
46 epoxidase (ZEP), enzymes catalyzing the de-epoxidation of V via A to Z and the epoxidation of Z via A
47 to V, respectively, were analyzed under various light conditions and compared with the wild type plant
48 (K326) as control. Lack of the two enzymes has significantly altered xanthophyll cycle pool size. In both
49 *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant, the content of V, A, Z, total xanthophyll cycle pool size and DEPS were
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1 all decreased significantly compared to those of wild type. However, the content of A, Z and DEPS in
2 *zep* were significantly higher than those of *vde* mutant (Fig. 7C – 7F).
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4 After transition from dark to low light, although value of NPQ parameter first briefly increased and
5 then decreased gradually, it was higher in *vde* and *zep* than those of wild type (WT). In transition from
6 the low light to high light, the value of NPQ parameter was always higher in WT than in *vde* and *zep* and
7 the increase of NPQ was faster in the WT than in the mutants (Fig. 7H). On the other hand, in the opposite
8 transition from high light to low light, the value of NPQ parameter was always smaller in WT than in
9 *vde* and *zep* and the decrease of NPQ parameter was faster in the WT than in the mutants (Fig. 7H).
10 Under fluctuating light conditions, the Φ PSII was always higher in WT than of *vde* and *zep* during all
11 light transitions, however, *zep* approached values of WT with increasing number of low-light regimes
12 (Fig. 7I).
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23 **Defects in VDE and ZEP reduced seedlings growth under fluctuating light conditions**

24 To further investigate the effects of xanthophyll cycle pigments on regulating plants growth under
25 fluctuating light conditions, growth of WT plants and of *VDE* and *ZEP* knockout mutants were analyzed
26 by determining maximum leaf area under constant and fluctuating light conditions. Under both constant
27 and fluctuating light conditions, the WT plants demonstrate a stable growth rate (Fig. 8). In contrast, both
28 mutants that defect in VDE and ZEP activity showed reduced growth compared with those of WT.
29 Specifically, the growth of the both two mutants was significantly lower than that of the WT under
30 fluctuating light conditions (Fig. 8).
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40 **Discussion**

41 Due to shade from clouds or leaves moving in the wind, plants often experience large fluctuations in light
42 intensity and they need to balance the absorption and utilization of this energy appropriately (Slattery et
43 al., 2018; Taylor and Long 2017). The qE is a rapidly switchable mechanisms that protects plants from
44 photodamage caused by high light exposed by dissipating the excess absorbed energy as heat (Nicol et
45 al., 2019; Ruban and Wilson 2021). The current study demonstrated distinct differences in excess energy
46 dissipation capabilities between two tobacco cultivars under constant and fluctuating light conditions, as
47 evidenced by their NPQ characteristics. Analysis of xanthophyll cycle pigments under high light
48 intensities revealed substantial variations in the contents of V, A, Z, and the DEPS state. These findings
49 confirm that the xanthophyll cycle plays a crucial role in regulating energy dissipation, ultimately
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1 influencing growth differences between the two varieties. Furthermore, comparisons of NPQ and growth
2 between wild-type plants and xanthophyll cycle pigment mutants under both light conditions were
3 conducted. Collectively, these results indicate that the xanthophyll cycle modulates plants' ability to
4 dissipate excess light energy, impacting their growth under both constant and fluctuating light. This
5 provides valuable insights into enhancing photoprotection during shade-to-sun transitions in field
6 conditions during the vegetative stage, presenting a potential target for future research aimed at
7 increasing agricultural productivity.
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10 The introduction of elite crop varieties can significantly enhance agricultural productivity and
11 efficiency. However, there exists a potential risk that these varieties may not adapt well to local
12 environmental conditions, leading to growth impairments and subsequent yield reductions (Pixley et al.,
13 2023; Wang et al., 2023). Due to the volatile weather conditions influenced by factors such as cloud
14 cover and precipitation, crops in Guizhou area always face frequent and intense fluctuations in light
15 intensity during each spring (Fig. 1). Such sudden increases in light intensity would impair the
16 functionality of Photosystem II (PSII) and Photosystem I (PSI), leading to a reduction in photosynthesis
17 efficiency. When introducing elite tobacco varieties from abroad to the Guizhou area and other regions
18 with similar frequent and severe fluctuations in light intensity, such adaptability issues are likely to
19 emerge. Xiaofeng 8 is a local tobacco variety in Guizhou, which has the advantages of good disease
20 resistance, strong adaptability, fast growth rate, and high yield while K326 is a variety introduced from
21 the United States and was once widely planted in Guizhou area (Fig. 2). As no significant differences in
22 ETR, PSII, and NPQ between the two varieties under light intensity less than $600 \text{ photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ were
23 found (Fig. 3), combined with the actual changes in light intensity in the field, light intensity of 70 and
24 $1000 \text{ photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ was set to simulate a low and high light condition respectively in subsequent
25 experiments. On shift from dark to low light (Fig. 4A), no significant difference in NPQ activation were
26 detected while Xiaofeng 8 demonstrated a more pronounced increase in NPQ compared to K326 under
27 high light (Fig.4B), highlighted their distinct adaptability to dissipating excess light energy and
28 associated photoprotection mechanisms under high light environments.
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54 Interestingly, while NPQ was higher in Xiaofeng 8 than in K326 in high light (Fig. 5A), the ΦPSII
55 was the same in the high-light condition in both varieties (Fig. 5B). Since $\text{NPQ} = \Phi\text{NPQ}/\Phi\text{NO}$ and ΦPSII
56 + $\Phi\text{NPQ} + \Phi\text{NO} = 1$, where ΦNPQ and ΦNO are the quantum yields of the regulatory and constitutive
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1 non-photochemical quenching, respectively (reviewed in Lazár 2015), K326 must have higher value of
2 Φ_{NO} in high light than Xiaofeng 8. This higher value of Φ_{NO} then causes a lower Φ_{PSII} in K326 than
3 in Xiaofeng 8 in initial intervals of low light conditions (Fig. 5B). The lower Φ_{PSII} in the low-light
4 conditions might be the reason of smaller values of all growth parameters in K326 than in Xiaogeng 8 in
5 the field conditions, i.e., under fluctuating light (Fig. 2 B-F). It implies that a possibility to induce and
6 relax a high regulatory non-photochemical quenching by Xiaofeng 8 is the reason of its better growth
7 than of K326.
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10 Under fluctuating light conditions, higher efficiency in NPQ values adjustment is of great
11 importance for the survival and reproduction of plants in natural environments with frequent and drastic
12 changes in light intensity (Armbruster et al., 2014). The fluctuation patterns of NPQ of K326 and
13 Xiaofeng8 under fluctuating light indicate that both plants have the ability to adjust their NPQ values
14 according to changes in light intensity (Fig. 5A). However, differences in NPQ values between them on
15 shift from low to high light condition were also observed, which may be related to factors such as their
16 genetic background and physiological characteristics (Ruben and Wilson 2021). Actually, NPQ combines
17 several different mechanisms that vary in activation kinetics during low-to-high light transitions (Malnoë
18 2018; Long et al., 2022). Being the major and most rapidly induced component upon transfer of leaves
19 to high light, the activation of photoprotection through NPQ is initiated within seconds up to a few
20 minutes and requires acidification of the thylakoid lumen to activate VDE, which converts V to Z via the
21 intermediate A in the VAZ xanthophyll cycle (Bassi and Dall'Osto, 2021; Ruban 2016; Demmig-Adams
22 et al., 2020), thereby dissipating excess light energy as heat. The xanthophyll cycle constitutes a vital
23 photoprotective mechanism in plants subjected to high light intensities. DES, defined as the ratio of Z
24 and A to the total xanthophyll cycle pool size, serves as an indicator of xanthophyll cycle activity and
25 plant heat dissipation capacity (Johnson et al., 1993; Jahns et al., 2009). Although a rapid increase in A,
26 Z and DES contents during the initial irradiation phase upon exposure to high light intensity in K326 and
27 Xiaofeng8 were exhibited, the differences in the response pattern and content of above xanthophyll cycle
28 pigments between the two varieties have also been discovered (Fig. 6), underscoring their variation in
29 maintaining stable photosynthetic efficiency and growth under high light intensities.
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56 Gene deletion mutants serve as pivotal tools in deciphering intricate biological processes within
57 plants such as photosynthesis and signal transduction. We next employed *vde* and *zep* knockout mutants
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1 targeting the key enzymes VDE and ZEP, the enzyme converts Z back to V, within the xanthophyll cycle
2 (Demmig-Adams, 1990), aiming to elucidate the involvement of this cycle in modulating plant responses
3 to high light intensities under fluctuating light conditions. Compared with the wild-type (WT), the *vde*
4 and *zep* mutants have lower levels of related pigments, demonstrating that knocking out *VDE* and *ZEP*
5 genes altered plants xanthophyll cycling pigment content. Under simulated fluctuating light conditions,
6 the NPQ changes in *vde* and *zep* knockout mutants are similar to those in the WT, but due to the absence
7 of VDE and ZEP enzymes, making it unable to effectively synthesize Z and A, resulting in a weakened
8 or delayed NPQ response during high light periods compared to the WT. The changes in Φ PSII of the
9 *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant are similar to those of the WT, but may be due to the obstruction of the
10 xanthophyll cycle and dissipate excess light energy, which may increase the degree of photoinhibition
11 during high light periods, leading to a greater decrease in Φ PSII and photosynthesis efficiency (Fig. 7B).
12 Furthermore, the diminished growth rate of the *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant under fluctuating light
13 conditions were observed compared to those of WT, indicative of a reduced adaptability to variable light
14 environments. These above research results together highlighting the crucial role of xanthophyll cycle
15 and its regulation of the NPQ in regulating plant light adaptation and improving growth under fluctuating
16 light conditions.

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33 In conclusion, our research findings offered compelling evidence elucidating the variation of NPQ
34 values among different plant varieties under the same lighting conditions, highlighted the crucial role of
35 the xanthophyll cycle, particularly the *VDE* and *ZEP* genes, in dissipating excess light energy and
36 safeguarding photosynthesis in plants under fluctuating light conditions. By studying mutants and
37 elucidating the functions of related genes, we found that optimizing the expression of these genes can
38 enhance light adaptability and productivity in plants, offering promise for sustainable agriculture and
39 food security. Furthermore, the complexity and genetic diversity of factors affecting plant NPQ under
40 fluctuating light conditions emphasize the importance of exploring genetic resources from both domestic
41 and imported varieties. This diversity provides valuable material for selecting and breeding new crop
42 varieties with improved yield, quality, and resistance, ultimately enhancing breeding efficiency and crop
43 adaptability.

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1 **Distinct non-photochemical quenching characteristics under constant and fluctuating light**
2 **conditions: comparison between local and imported tobacco varieties**
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Figure legends

Figure 1. Ten-day average sunshine hour and 10-d average temperature from April to October at Qingzhen in 2023.

Figure 2. Comparison of growth of K326 and Xiaofeng 8 seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d. (A) Phenotype of K326 (right ridge) and Xiaofeng 8 (left ridge) in the field. (B to F) Leaf number (B), maximum leaf area (C), plant height (D), plant fresh weight (E) and dry weight (F) of seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d in Qingzhen, 2022. Data are presented as means \pm S.E.. (n > 10 biological replicates) and the different letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

Figure 3. Kinetics of NPQ (A and B) and Φ_{PSII} (C and D) on transition from dark to constant low light (70 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, A and C) and constant high light (1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, B and D). Measurements were made after 30 min dark adaptation in the seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d in Qingzhen, 2022. Data are the means \pm S.E.. Where not visible, error bars are smaller than the symbols.

Figure 4. Light dependence of steady-state chlorophyll fluorescence parameters of the relative PSII electron transport rate (ETR, A), quantum yield of PSII photochemistry in light-adapted state (Φ_{PSII} , B), and the non-photochemical quenching parameter (NPQ, C) in seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d in Qingzhen, 2022. Each point represents the mean of 5 measurements and error bars indicate the S.E. and the asterisk in (C) indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 5. Dynamics of NPQ parameter (A) and Φ_{PSII} (B) to fluctuating light conditions simulated by four cycles of 3 min low light ($70 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, gray background) and 3 min high light ($1000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, white background) as indicated. Measurements were made after 30 min dark adaptation in the seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d in Qingzhen, 2022. Data are the means \pm S.E. Where not visible, error bars are smaller than the symbols.

Figure 6. Changes in the content of violaxanthin (A), antheraxanthin (B), zeaxanthin (C), and the xanthophyll cycle de-epoxidation state (DEPS, D) during illumination with 1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in the youngest mature leaves of K326 and Xiaofeng 8 seedlings grown in the field after transplanting for 20 d in Qingzhen, 2022. Fully expanded leaves of seedlings that prior dark adapted for 30 min were collected after 0, 1 min, 5 min, 10 min, 20 min and 30 min of illumination at 1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. Data represent means \pm S.E. of $n=5$ individual plants. If not shown, S.E. is smaller than symbol.

Figure 7. (A) and (B), Generation of mutations in *VDE* (LOC104218706, A) and *ZEP* (LOC104218557, B) by CRISPR–Cas9, using a single-guide RNA. Sequences of *VDE* and *ZEP* in wild-type (WT) and *vde* and *zep* mutant plants are shown. The deletion is indicated by a dashed line. (C–F), Contents of violaxanthin (C), antheraxanthin (D), zeaxanthin (E), and the xanthophyll cycle de-epoxidation state (DEPS, F) in 60-day-old wild type (K326), *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant plants. (G) and (H), Dynamics of NPQ parameter (G) and Φ_{PSII} (H) to fluctuating light conditions simulated by four cycles of 3 min low light (70 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, gray bars) and 3 min high light (1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, white bars) as indicated in K326, *vde* and *zep* knockout mutant plants grown under constant light (1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Seedlings that were 45-day-old were moved to growth chamber with a 16/8 light/dark cycle and a constant light intensity of 1000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. For (H) and (I), measurements were made after 30 min dark adaptation in more than five fully individual plants. Data are the means \pm S.E.. Where not visible, error bars are smaller than the symbols, the different letters in (C–F) indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 8. Growth rates of xanthophyll cycle mutants and WT plants under constant and fluctuating light conditions. Plant growth and linear regressions (circles and lines) growth rates were measured and calculated as change in maximum leaf area in (A) and (B). Growth phenotype of *vde*, *zep* knockout mutants and WT plants grown under constant (C) and fluctuating light conditions (D). Data show the mean with standard deviation of n=5 biological independent samples. Black symbols indicate constant light, red symbols fluctuating light conditions, respectively. Time axes give days after transplanting. From linear regressions (solid and dashed lines) growth rates were calculated.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: